

From Threat to Triumph: Preventing, Diagnosing, and Controlling Avian Influenza

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Avian/bird flu is a fearful viral disease of birds, caused by Avian Influenza Virus (AIV). H5N1 subtype of AIV is of major concern for poultry as well as for humans due to its high economic impacts and zoonotic concerns. Over 60 countries worldwide have been affected by the Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) H5N1 subtype alone in the last ten years. The difference between low pathogenicity (LP) viruses and high pathogenicity (HP) viruses can be as small as a single amino acid change in the hemagglutinin (HA) fusion cleavage site. Therefore, it is important not only to assess an AI virus's ability to cause disease in poultry but also to assess the potential for AI viruses to cause disease in poultry. The disease primarily affects domestic poultry. The AIV reservoirs are wild and migratory birds, wherein H5N1 is found to be lethal. Periodic pandemics are caused by major antigenic changes in Haemagglutinin (HA) or Neuraminidase (NA). Pigs can act as a mixing vessel. Due to extreme genetic alteration, control is difficult. According to the World Health Organization, about 900 people were infected with H5N1 between 2003 and 2024; more than 50 per cent of those individuals died.

ETIOLOGY:

Avian bird flu is caused by avian influenza virus (AIV), which belongs to Type A influenza viruses under the genus *influenza virus A* of the family *Orthomyxoviridae*. AIV is a negative-sense,

single-stranded RNA (ssRNA) virus. Its causative agent, Avian Influenza Virus (AIV), can produce a wide spectrum of infection in poultry, ranging from subclinical to highly fatal outbreaks. The virus was first identified in 1878 in poultry flocks in Italy, and thereafter, disease outbreaks in poultry have been reported worldwide.

HOST RANGE:

The virus can naturally infect a wide variety of avian species, but primarily it causes a disease in domesticated poultry such as fowl and turkeys. Among these, turkeys are the most vulnerable, followed by chickens. Other susceptible species include quails, guinea fowls, pheasants, partridges, geese and ducks. Ostriches, passerine birds and pheasants can also be infected.

TRANSMISSION AND SPREAD:

The avian influenza virus is highly contagious and can spread very fast, with the potential to move across continents. Transmission occurs either through direct contact between infected and healthy birds or indirectly via airborne particles, contaminated feed, water, equipment, clothing, faeces, or other materials. The major route of transmission is the faeco-oral route. Wild/migratory/free-flying birds, as well as ducks and geese, are important reservoirs of influenza viruses.

These birds constantly shed the virus through their respiratory secretions and droppings, which helps the virus to persist in the environment. Pigs often act as a mixing vessel, leading to genetic recombination and the emergence of new strains.

CLINICAL SIGNS:

In domestic poultry, primarily chickens and turkeys, avian influenza typically causes a sudden onset of severe illness, leading to rapid deaths with morbidity and mortality rates that can approach 100% within just a few days. It is a fatal disease affecting multiple organs. In per acute cases, birds are seen dead without showing any clinical signs. Common symptoms include severe respiratory distress with abnormal sounds, depression, coughing, sneezing, watery eyes, excessive eye discharges, cyanosis of the head, combs, wattles, shanks, and a drop in egg production. Swelling of the head, face, and sinuses, along with ruffled feathers and diarrhoea—bright green at first and turning white later—are also observed.

PATHOLOGY:

The most commonly observed lesions include petechial haemorrhages across the entire viscera and peritoneum, along with congestion and swelling around the eyes (periorbital oedema). Haemorrhages in different organs, especially epicardium (pinpoint haemorrhages), pectoral muscles, mucosa proventriculus and gizzard, with areas of necrotic foci also seen. Death usually results from multiple organ failure.

PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE:

Influenza A viruses infect a variety of animal species, including humans, pigs, horses, marine mammals and birds. The virus has expanded its host range and has

infected dogs and other mammals. Only HPAI viruses have been reported to have zoonotic importance.

CLINICAL FEATURES OF BIRD FLU IN HUMANS:

The risk of transmission to humans increases when there is close proximity of birds to humans. The incubation period for AIV in humans is probably between 3-7 days. Clinical signs include a rapid onset of severe viral pneumonia with a high fatality rate, fever, sore throat, cough, breathing problems (acute respiratory distress), chest pain, muscle aches, fatigue, and lethargy. Eye infections (conjunctivitis), severe bilateral pneumonia, myocarditis (inflammation of the heart muscle), and other severe and life-threatening complications can occur.

DIAGNOSIS:

Tentatively diagnosis of avian influenza is made by observing clinical signs and very high flock mortality. For confirmatory diagnosis, it requires isolation, identification and characterisation of the virus from suspected samples, i.e. tracheal/cloacal swabs, faeces, tissue samples including trachea, lungs, etc. Definitive diagnosis requires direct detection of AI viral antigen/nucleic acid in affected tissues, swabs, clinical samples and inoculated cell cultures or embryonating chicken eggs. For demonstration of viral antigen in the suspected clinical samples, the techniques employed are Agar Gel Immunodiffusion (AGID), Immunofluorescence Test (IFT), and Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assays (ELISA). Detection of antibodies to the AI virus by AGID and HI tests is of significant value. Virus Neutralization Test (VNT), IFT, and ELISA are important diagnostic tools.

TREATMENT:

There is no specific treatment for birds. They are just given supportive therapy; for example, to reduce secondary bacterial infection, they are provided with antibiotics. Medications against influenza, such as Zanamivir (Relenza) and Oseltamivir (Tamiflu), can be used not only for the treatment of individuals infected with bird flu but also for preventing the disease in those at risk of exposure. Along with antipyretic medications, suitable anti-inflammatory drugs are also prescribed. Tamiflu is the neuraminidase inhibitor which checks the flu viruses from multiplying within the host cell and is found to be most effective. Tamiflu is the drug of choice. Various herbs play a substantial role in promoting the host's immunity.

PREVENTION AND CONTROL:

Prevention of avian influenza in poultry primarily depends upon strict biosecurity measures. Human traffic needs to be checked, and visitors are to be avoided. Employees must wear clean clothing daily, and disinfectant boot dips should be used. Contact with migratory or wild birds must be avoided, and accumulation of standing and stagnant water should be prevented to reduce attraction for waterfowl. Employees of the poultry farm house need to be educated about the dangers of live bird markets, which are a potent source of AIV infection. Sick or dead birds must be disposed of by burial or incineration. Infected flocks should be culled through proper procedures, followed by disinfection of premises. Surveillance and monitoring of the Avian influenza virus should be followed regularly to know the disease status. Epidemiological investigations with strict biosecurity measures are followed to prevent further spread. Restocking should only be done after the recommended waiting period and protocols to ensure safety. Vaccines are some

of the best tools to prevent widespread and severe disease caused by influenza viruses and for protection against various H5 influenza viruses. Since bird flu is classified as a *notifiable disease*, any outbreak should be immediately reported to the regulatory authorities. Only trained veterinarians and professionals wearing protective gloves, masks, etc, as biosafety measures should handle suspected birds.

CONCLUSION:

Influenza A viruses are important pathogens affecting both veterinary and human health around the world. Avian influenza (AI) virus in poultry is unique because it can cause a range of disease symptoms from a sub-clinical infection to a highly lethal form causing 100% flock mortality. AI viruses infect a wide variety of hosts, including mammals, and can represent a zoonotic risk. Additionally, the main reservoir for the AI viruses is in wild aquatic birds; therefore, complete eradication is not possible. All these factors make AI viruses an important but difficult pathogen to control in poultry. Progress in vaccinology is being utilized to design safer and more effective vaccines for protecting birds as well as humans against the AIV H5N1 subtype. Developing and implementing strong, well-designed strategies is essential to prevent the bird flu virus before it changes its genes (through mutation or reassortment), becomes more dangerous, and gains the ability to spread quickly from person to person, which could result in a severe global pandemic.

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